

Changes in Students' Attitudes Towards Econometrics during and Introductory Course: Are There Any Gender Differences?

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Abstract

The current job market demands professionals with knowledge and skills related to data analysis. However, many students in Social Sciences, including Economics, have difficulties when dealing with subjects of quantitative methods, such as econometrics. It can harm their employability and be more problematic for women, who tend to show less interest in STEM subjects than men. Previous research has shown that students' attitudes affect their ability to acquire content and skills. Positive attitudes can improve different aspects of their learning, such as their performance, the ability to use what they have learned in the future, and their chances of furthering their study of the subject. Since econometrics is the dominant subject related to data analysis in undergraduate studies of Economics, this study aims to investigate students' attitudes towards econometrics throughout the course and its relationship with gender. There is a significant lack of research on these issues in the field, and this study is the first to analyse the differences in the attitudinal dimensions from the beginning to the end of the course and their relationship with gender. Results reveal gender differences in attitudes and their evolution and that the changes in the attitudinal components throughout the course are neutral or negative.

Keywords: econometrics, students' attitudes, gender, SATS.

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Introduction

The digitization process that today's society is undergoing is generating more and more data in all areas. Along with this, there is an urgent need for data experts who can inform and support the decision-making of the different social agents. Accordingly, the labour market increasingly appreciates data skills and quantitative methods-related knowledge (Angrist & Pischke, 2017; Carter et al., 2017; Conaway et al., 2018; Hermans et al., 2022; Smaldone et al., 2022; Terry, 2019).

Universities must respond to these labour market needs by preparing their students to develop their professional future and be competitive in this environment. As reported by Potocan et al. (2021), the newest demands of society require that universities, as the principal developers of knowledge, be capable of training their students in the appropriate abilities and competencies for working in current conditions. However, the literature has pointed out that social sciences, and specifically undergraduate Economics and Business students do not generally have the necessary mathematical foundations to face quantitative methods courses, such as econometrics (Becker & Greene, 2001; Bohórquez Gómez-Millán & Checa Esquivá, 2019; Cook et al., 2019; Marí-Klose & Gallo de Puelles, 2016). Papers on the teaching of econometrics have highlighted the difficulties that lecturers of this subject encounter (Angrist & Pischke, 2017; Becker & Greene, 2001; Gibbs, 2010). The main challenge is to attract and motivate students, as they often find econometrics courses complex and unappealing. Students usually consider econometrics courses complicated, stressful, and anxiety-inducing. As a result, it is difficult for them to gain knowledge and skills in this subject. Therefore, there appears to be a mismatch between the demands of the labour market and the low inclination of Economics students towards econometrics courses. Consequently, to prepare students for the requirements of the labour market, it is necessary to address the negative attitudes that many of them have towards quantitative methods and, specifically, econometrics, which can hinder the acquisition of skills in these subjects.

These negative attitudes might be more concerning for female students due to gender differences in the preferences for specific fields. For instance, previous studies reveal that women tend to be less interested in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) subjects than men (e.g., Barone, 2011; Carrell et al., 2010; Charles & Bradley, 2009; DiPrete & Buchmann, 2013; Dökme et al., 2022; Gabay-Egozi et al., 2015; Hermans et al., 2022; Zafar, 2013).

Studies have also noted gender differences in the preferences for Economics. Early research by Dynan & Rouse (1997) suggested that the underrepresentation of women in Economics was due to preconceptions about the subjects, which made them find it uninteresting. Additionally, Kaleva et al. (2019) found that women aged 16 had significantly less interest in Economics than men. Other studies (eg. Bansak & Starr, 2010; Tonin & Wahba, 2015) also confirm a lower enrolment and interest by women in the study of Economics.

Focusing on econometrics, research on students' attitudes towards the subject is really limited; however, a rich literature has analysed students' attitudes towards the related discipline of statistics and has assessed the existence of gender differences. Most of this research has revealed that women often have more negative attitudes than men (e.g. Crettaz von Roten & de Roten, 2023; Opstad, 2020; Stanisavljevic et al., 2014). Cladera (2021) initiates work on this topic in the field of econometrics: using an adaptation of the Survey of Attitudes Towards Statistics (SATS) (Schau, 2003b), she measures students' attitudes toward econometrics and finds that women have more positive attitudes than men in some particular dimensions related to effort and difficulty. Such a finding might seem counter-intuitive: one would expect similar patterns in econometrics and statistics since both are related disciplines. Hence, there is a need for further analysis of gender differences in attitudes towards econometrics. Cladera (2021) also suggests adopting a dynamic approach to measuring attitudes. While she measures attitudes at a particular moment, she indicates that a better approach would consider that students' attitudes might change from the beginning to the end of the course. Hence, the importance of measuring and analysing such a change. Evaluating students' attitudes at the end of the course -as done with other course outcomes, such as students' performance- and comparing them with attitudes at the beginning would allow lecturers to check to what extent the course has achieved the objective of developing positive attitudes towards the discipline.

Within this context, the present study aims to contribute to filling the identified gap in the literature regarding the analysis of the evolution of students' attitudes towards econometrics over the course and their relationship with students' characteristics, in particular, gender. For this purpose, the study collected data by surveying Economics undergraduate students at two Spanish universities, the University of Oviedo and the University of the Balearic Islands. The survey was administered at the beginning and end of the course to track the evolution of attitudes. The information retrieved allowed for obtaining detailed information on the students' attitudes and the differences between men and women.

Assessing attitudes, their evolution, and gender-based differences is the first step towards articulating measures that improve the learning process and address the different needs of men and women. The results open a discussion on improvements and teaching innovations consistent with the findings.

The paper is organized as follows: the next section presents a review of previous research on the analysis of students' attitudes and their differences by gender. Then, the theoretical framework is explained and subsequently, the aim of the study and the research hypothesis are stated. The following section introduces the survey instrument administered to collect student responses and describes the statistical methodologies applied for data analysis. Next, the results obtained are presented. Finally, the main findings are discussed.

Background

The literature recognizes the critical importance of students' attitudes in their learning processes (e.g. Gal et al., 1997; Ramirez et al., 2010, 2012). Students' attitudes towards a subject are key since they influence content and skills acquisition.

Negative attitudes are an obstacle to both learning and the proper use in the future of what has been learned (Fullerton & Umphrey, 2001). Students who exhibit negative attitudes at the end of a course probably never will use its content in their professional, personal or educational future, or if they do, they will not use it appropriately (Schau & Emmioğlu, 2012).

In turn, students' positive attitudes towards a subject improve their learning, performance, willingness to expand knowledge, and capacity to properly use what has been learned (Ashaari et al., 2011; Batanero, 1999; Carnell, 2008; Gal et al., 1997; Garfield et al., 2002).

Accordingly, developing students' positive attitudes towards a subject should be a key objective in the learning process for every lecturer (Schau & Emmioğlu, 2012). Lecturers not only must teach content; they also have to demonstrate the discipline's relevance for students' future careers and arouse their interest to expand their knowledge in the field and apply it in their professional future. It is particularly crucial in introductory courses, where students encounter the subject matter for the first time, and even more so in inherently challenging subjects, such as statistics and econometrics.

The effect of students' attitudes on the learning of Statistics is a matter widely investigated (e.g., Ashaari et al., 2011; Carnell, 2008; Gal et al., 1997; Garfield et al., 2002; Schau & Emmioğlu, 2012). However, this is not the case for econometrics, where there is scarce evidence.

In the field of Statistics, to measure the multidimensional nature of attitudes, most research has relied on the SATS scale (Schau et al., 1995) This instrument is a seven-point Likert-type questionnaire. The first version had 28 items to assess four attitudinal dimensions: Affect, Cognitive Competence, Value, and Difficulty. Two additional dimensions, Interest and Effort, were added to the updated version, resulting in 36 items (SATS-36). Extensive research supports the reliability, validity, and multi-dimensionality of the SATS scores and constructs (e.g., Chiesi & Primi, 2010; Coetzee & Van Der Merwe, 2010; Persson et al., 2019; Tempelaar, Gijsselaers, et al., 2007; Tempelaar, Van Der Loeff, et al., 2007; Vanhoof et al., 2011).

Results have shown that students' attitudes towards Statistics (and Mathematics) differ depending on characteristics such as gender, age, achievement, and expected grade (e.g. Berger et al., 2020; Cladera et al., 2019, 2021; Emmioğlu & Capa-Aydin, 2012; Hannigan et al., 2014; Hemmings & Kay, 2010; Mills, 2004; Opstad, 2020; Parnis & Petocz, 2016; Stanisavljevic et al., 2014; Valenzuela-Ocana & Miranda-Valenzuela, 2021).

Specifically, extensive cross-country evidence reveals that attitudes towards statistics differ significantly by gender in numerous majors. Most studies point in the direction of women showing worse attitudes than men in most attitudinal dimensions. For example, at the University

of Florence in Italy, Chiesi & Primi (2015) found that female attitudes tend to be more negative since they usually underestimate their abilities and are less self-confident. Valenzuela-Ocana & Miranda-Valenzuela (2021) show that, at Tecnológico de Monterrey in Mexico, the impact of incorporating new learning methodologies to improve engagement in statistics is not the same for men and women, being less beneficial for the latter.

Such results are confirmed by a series of works that, relying on the SATS scale (Schau, 2003b), have revealed that women have significantly more negative attitudes on particular dimensions of this scale (Bechrakisa et al., 2011; Crettaz von Roten & de Roten, 2023; Opstad, 2020; Rejón-Guardia et al., 2019; Stanisavljevic et al., 2014; van Es & Weaver, 2018). Using data from a university in Greece, (Bechrakisa et al., 2011) finds that females have more negative attitudes in the Affective, Cognitive and Difficulty dimensions. For the University of Belgrade (Serbia), Stanisavljevic et al. (2014) found that males had higher Cognitive attitudes than females; however, they did not find significant differences for the rest of the SATS dimensions. For the University of Balearic Islands (Spain), Rejón-Guardia et al. (2019) obtained significant differences in the dimensions of Affect, Value, Difficulty and Effort, with women showing more negative attitudes than men in all of them, except for the Effort dimension, where women had a higher mean score. Similarly, at Cornell University (U.S.), Van Es & Weaver, (2018) show that female students score lower in Affect, Cognitive Competency and Difficulty dimensions. In the case of a Norwegian business school, Opstad's (2020) results suggest that women are less motivated than men. He also finds that men score significantly higher in the dimensions of Value, Difficulty and Interest and also higher but with less difference concerning women in Affect and Cognitive competence. Effort would be the only dimension in which women score significantly higher than men. Crettaz von Roten & de Roten (2023), analyze the attitudes towards statistics of sports students at the University of Lausanne (Switzerland) and find that men show better attitudes than women in the Affect and Cognitive competence dimensions at the end of the course.

In contrast to this burgeoning literature for Statistics, the related case of Econometrics remains practically unexplored. So far, the exception is Cladera (2021); she uses SATS-36 to investigate students' attitudes towards econometrics and finds that attitudes vary according to students' expected grades in the course, gender, and prior interest in the subject. Her results show that women have more positive attitudes in the Effort and Difficulty dimensions. Therefore, given the lack of research in this field, it is of particular interest to further analyse gender differences in attitudes towards econometrics, especially when this kind of quantitative analysis skills are increasingly demanded and valued in the labour market (Cook et al., 2019).

Theoretical framework

The study of students' attitudes toward different fields of study, specifically statistics, has been framed within the context of various pedagogical theories, such as the Self-determination Theory, Self-Efficacy Theory, Achievement Goal Theory, and, notably, Eccles' Expectancy-Value Theory

(EVT) (Ramirez et al., 2012). Eccles' EVT (Eccles et al., 1983) posits that students' beliefs about their likelihood of success in a task and how much they value that task are related and predict students' performance accordingly. In other words, EVT suggests that students are more likely to engage in and succeed in tasks they generally value and expect to perform well in. When applied to econometrics, these tasks may include learning the subject, implementing econometrics in their academic and professional lives, or selecting further econometrics courses.

These theories provided the framework within which the Survey of Attitudes Towards Statistics (SATS) (Schau et al., 1995) was developed. Ramirez et al. (2012) explain that the six dimensions of the SATS are related to components of Eccles' EVT. Therefore, EVT contextualizes value (referred to as Subjective Task Value) as a super-construct that cannot be directly measured but includes several measurable components, such as students' interest (Interest) and enjoyment of the task (Affect), the importance they attach to the task and its utility for their future (Value), and the effort (Effort) required to complete the task. Additionally, Eccles' EVT includes constructs of task difficulty (Difficulty) and self-concept of their abilities (Cognitive Competence). EVT also incorporates the impact of Student Characteristics, such as gender or age, and Previous Achievement-Related Experiences on attitudes and other outcomes.

Therefore, within the framework of EVT, it is recognized that student characteristics, such as gender, may affect attitudes. Wang & Degol (2013) use EVT to study gender differences in STEM areas and explain how beliefs related to expectations of success and the value associated with the different options available are influenced by cultural norms, behaviour genetics, social experiences, aptitudes, and the affective reactions of previous experiences. Therefore, it is likely that male and female differences in STEM field selection are associated with gendered differences in these motivational beliefs (e.g., self-efficacy, interests, and task value).

Thus, EVT provides a theoretical framework to analyse differences in attitudes between men and women towards specific areas of study, particularly econometrics.

Aim and research hypotheses

The objective of this paper is twofold: firstly, to assess students' attitudes towards econometrics at the beginning and the end of the course and measure their changes; secondly, to investigate if differences in attitudes and their evolution throughout the course differ by gender.

Concerning these objectives, the following research hypotheses were raised:

1. Students' attitudes towards econometrics differ from the beginning to the end of the course.
2. Changes in attitudes differ depending on students' gender.

As mentioned, the Expectancy Value Theory incorporates the impact of students' characteristics and experiences on attitudes. Therefore, exposure to the subject during their first econometrics course and gender can affect students' attitudes.

Materials and methods

Participants

The population considered for the study were undergraduate Economics students enrolled in a compulsory introductory course in econometrics at the University of the Balearic Islands and the University of Oviedo, both in Spain. The nature of the course is introductory. It is the first one they have on econometrics, and it introduces the concepts, procedures, and basic tools of econometrics, such as the linear regression model and its extensions. Teaching focuses on both the review of theoretical content and the completion of practical exercises and practices using econometric software. The study was conducted during the academic year 2022-23, with 136 students enrolled.

Survey instrument

The researchers used a self-administered questionnaire to assess students' attitudes towards econometrics. This instrument included an adaptation of the SATS to measure attitudes towards econometrics (Cladera, 2021). The SATS scale has 36 items for assessing six dimensions: Affect, Cognitive Competence, Value, Difficulty, Interest, and Effort. It is a seven-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Not at all agree) to 7 (Totally agree). In addition, the questionnaire includes questions regarding sociodemographic and academic characteristics of students, such as course section, gender, and age. The survey also asks two questions about their interest in the subject before the course and the expected grade in the course. The same questionnaire was administered at the beginning and the end of the course, changing the tense since minimal adjustments were necessary in wording due to the different timing of administration.

The survey was administered over two days, during which the students had to carry out compulsory activities - one at the beginning and the other at the end of the course. The method for selecting the sample was convenience sampling, where the researchers invited to participate to all the students who were in class on the selected days. After completing the activity and before finishing the lecture, one of the researchers asked them to answer the questionnaire by accessing a Google Forms form. The researcher explained to the students the objectives and informed them that participation was voluntary, and responses and the entire process would be completely anonymous. In the pre-test, 103 students responded to the questionnaire, and 74 in the post-test. The number of students who answered both questionnaires was 50.

Analytical methods

In their analysis of the attitudes scale data, the authors followed the guidelines of three sources: (i) the SATS website (Schau, 2003b) , (ii) previous studies that had used the scale in the field of Statistics (such as Millar & Schau, 2010 and Schau & Emmioğlu, 2012), and (iii) the work of Cladera (2021), who modified the SATS to measure attitudes towards econometrics.

The first step was to reverse the negatively worded items of the SATS scale, according to the recommendations of the SATS website (Schau, 2003b) , so allowing to interpret all the

items in the same way: the higher the item score, the better the attitude towards that item. Secondly, Cronbach's alpha was calculated for the total scale and each attitudinal dimension to analyse their reliability. Then, the items of the scale were analysed; the mean and standard deviation were calculated for each item, both in the pre and post-samples separately and in the matched sample. The same was done for the six dimensions of the SATS. Finally, differences in the average scores of each of the six dimensions of the SATS based on the academic and demographic characteristics of the students were investigated, paying particular attention to the analysis of gender differences.

Following the instructions of Millar & Schau (2010) and Schau & Emmioğlu (2012), when assessing differences in attitudes, those equal to or greater than $\frac{1}{2}$ have been considered of practical significance. Additionally, various tests have been used to complement the analyses. When comparing differences in attitudes between men and women in the pre-test and post-test, t-tests for equality of means for independent samples have been used for components with a normal distribution, and the Mann-Whitney U test for those that did not meet the normality assumption. For examining whether there were changes in attitudes from the beginning to the end of the course, tests for paired samples have been employed, using the t-test for normally distributed components and the Wilcoxon test for non-normal components. To investigate the existence of differences in attitudes based on other student characteristics besides gender, ANOVA and Kruskal-Wallis tests were used for normally and non-normally distributed components, respectively. Finally, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test has been used to test the normality of the attitudinal components.

Results

Sample characteristics

Table 1 summarises the characteristics of the collected sample and shows the percentage of students responding to each of the categories of the variables. The results obtained in the pre-test and post-test are presented, as well as the results for the matched observations, both for the whole sample and disaggregated by gender.

Regarding the level of interest in econometrics, the percentage of students showing a high or a very high interest in the subject increases at the end of the course. The difference by gender is noteworthy, with women reporting a higher interest than men in both the pre and the post-test. However, the difference is lower in the post-test results, indicating that men's interest in the subject increases more during the course.

As for the grades obtained in related subjects, most students get a grade between 5 and 7 points out of 10 in statistics. As for the differences by gender, there is a higher percentage (7.7% versus 17.4%) of women with a grade higher than 9 in this subject and mathematics (referring to the grades obtained before entering university). Most students had a grade of remarkable or

excellent, the percentage being slightly higher for women. Concerning the expected grade in econometrics, the expectation decreases at the end of the course.

Regarding the usefulness of econometrics in their professional life, results show that the share of students that consider it useful or very useful is practically the same in the pre-and the post-test, although there are differences by gender. A higher percentage of women than men consider that econometrics is useful or very useful at the beginning of the course. However, by the end of the course, a higher percentage of male students find econometrics more useful than female students.

As for the rest of the variables, the expected hours of study per week show that most students report to study between 2 and 7 hours per week. The percentages of students by gender show that there are more or less half of students of each gender, with slightly fewer female students. Most students are enrolling in the subject for the first time and the average age is around 21 years.

Table 1. Sample Characteristics.

		Matched									
		Pre-test sample		Post-test sample		Total		Male		Female	
		(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
Level of interest in econometrics	Very small	4.9	2.0	2.0	2.7	2.0	2.0			4.3	4.3
	Small	11.7	12.0	10.0	16.4	10.0	12.0	11.1	14.8	8.7	8.7
	Normal	55.3	44.0	60.0	47.9	60.0	44.0	66.7	44.4	52.2	43.5
	High	23.3	32.0	22.0	26.0	22.0	32.0	18.5	29.6	26.1	34.8
	Very high	4.9	10.0	6.0	6.8	6.0	10.0	3.7	11.1	8.7	8.7
Grade in Statistics	<3										
	3-5	3.0		4.1		4.1		3.8		4.3	
	5-7	57.6		49.0		49.0		53.8		43.5	
	7-9	29.3		34.7		34.7		34.6		34.8	
	>9	10.1		12.2		12.2		7.7		17.4	
Usual grade in Mathematics	Failed	4.9		2.0		2.0				4.3	
	Pass	16.5		10.0		10.0		18.5			
	Remarkable	41.7		44.0		44.0		40.7		47.8	
	Excellent	36.9		44.0		44.0		40.7		47.8	
Expected grade in econometrics	<3										
	3-5	1.0	10.0	2.0	6.8	2.0	10.0	3.7	7.4		13.0
	5-7	61.2	64.0	66.0	74.3	66.0	64.0	70.4	74.1	60.9	52.2
	7-9	33.0	24.0	28.0	16.2	28.0	24.0	18.5	14.8	39.1	34.8
	>9	4.9	2.0	4.0	2.7	4.0	2.0	7.4	3.7		
Usefulness of Econometrics for professional life	Not at all	4.9	12.0	6.0	10.8	6.0	12.0	11.1	11.1		13.0
	Not very useful	16.5	12.0	18.0	18.9	18.0	12.0	11.1	11.1	26.1	13.0
	Medium	47.6	40.0	44.0	39.2	44.0	40.0	48.1	40.7	39.1	39.1
	Useful	23.3	30.0	22.0	25.7	22.0	30.0	29.6	33.3	13.0	26.1
	Very useful	7.8	6.0	10.0	5.4	10.0	6.0		3.7	21.7	8.7
Expected study hours per week	0-2	9.7		8.0		8.0		11.1		4.3	
	2-5	43.7		44.0		44.0		37.0		52.2	
	5-7	35.9		40.0		40.0		44.4		34.8	
	7-12	9.7		8.0		8.0		7.4		8.7	
	>12	1.0									
Gender	Male	58.3	54.0	54.0	52.7	54.0	54.0				
	Female	41.7	46.0	46.0	47.3	46.0	46.0				

Repeater	Yes	11.7	14.0	12.0	21.6	12.0	14.0	14.8	14.8	8.7	8.7
	No	88.3	86.0	88.0	78.4	88.0	86.0	85.2	85.2	91.3	91.3
		Mean									
Age		21.8	21.0	22.0	22.0	22.0	21.0	21.8		20.2	
n		103	50	50	74	50		27		23	

(1) Beginning of the course; (2) End of the course

Economics students' attitudes towards econometrics

The first step was to evaluate the reliability of the SATS scale by calculating the Cronbach alpha. For the pre-test, the values of this statistic were 0.87 for the total scale and 0.78, 0.75, 0.80, 0.60, 0.87, and 0.81 for the Affect, Cognitive Competence, Value, Difficulty, Interest, and Effort dimensions, respectively. The values of the Cronbach alpha in the pre-test were 0.93 for the total scale and 0.83, 0.77, 0.85, 0.68, 0.92, and 0.75 for the Affect, Cognitive Competence, Value, Difficulty, Interest, and Effort dimensions, respectively. Following the rule of thumb suggested by Stephanie (2020), the Cronbach alpha could be questionable only for the Difficulty scale. The lower Cronbach alpha in the Difficulty dimension is in line with previous studies, which found the reliability of this dimension to be usually the lowest, with values that can often be questionable (e.g., Cahyawati et al., 2018; Cladera, 2021; Coetzee & Van Der Merwe, 2010; Dauphinee et al., 1997; García-Santillán et al., 2014; Hilton et al., 2004; Schau, 2008; Schau et al., 1995; Tempelaar, Van Der Loeff, et al., 2007). Subsequently, the normality of attitude components was tested using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test: in the pre-test, Interest and Effort violated the normality assumption; in the post-test, Value and Difficulty did not meet the normality assumption. Regarding the difference scores, the normality assumption does not hold for Value, Interest, and Effort. These results have been considered to select the appropriate tests to analyse the differences in attitudes.

Table 2 reports the mean scores for the items and dimensions of the attitude measurement scale. In the Affect dimension, the average score is around 4 for both the pre and post-test, meaning that attitudes in this dimension are neutral. The two items within this dimension with the highest scores are items “3. I have liked econometrics” and “28. I am scared by econometrics”, which show a mean slightly higher than four. Contrarily, those items with the lowest mean scores are “4. I still feel insecure when I have to do econometrics exercises” and “18. I have been under stress during econometrics classes”, showing mean scores of around 3 points.

For Cognitive Competence, the mean score is slightly superior to four points, indicating that attitudes regarding this dimension are somewhat positive for the pre-test and the post-test. As for the breakdown by items, items “11. I have no idea of what’s going on in this econometrics course” and “31. I could learn econometrics” stand out with a mean score above 5, meaning that attitudes in these aspects are positive. The only item within the Cognitive dimension with a mean score below 4 is “35. I have found it difficult to understand econometrics concepts”.

The Value dimension has a mean score of almost five points at the beginning of the course and around 4.5 at the end of the semester. Except for the item “17. I use econometrics in my

everyday life", with an average score close to 3 points, the rest exceed 4 points, especially highlighting the item "7. Econometrics is worthless" with a mean score above 6, and the item "33. Econometrics is irrelevant in my life" with a score above 5.2 points in the pre-test.

As for the Difficulty dimension, this is the one that shows the lowest mean scores, indicating that attitudes in this dimension are negatives. All the items included here show a mean of less than 4, being especially low in items "22. Econometrics is a subject quickly learned by most people" and "24. Learning econometrics requires a great deal of discipline", which have a mean score of around 2.5 points.

The mean score of the Interest dimension is almost 5, indicating that attitudes in this regard are slightly positive. All the items that compound this dimension have mean scores above 4.5 points in the pre-test. Finally, the Effort dimension is the one that exhibits the highest mean, which is around six points in the pre-test and 5 in the post-test. Item "1. I have done all my econometrics assignments" stands out with a mean score of around six points.

According to these findings, the attitudes towards econometrics of the surveyed students do not seem negative: all the dimensions, except Difficulty, obtain mean scores close to the value that indicates neutrality or slightly above. These results agree with the previous study of Cladera (2021) in the field of econometrics and with previous research in the area of Statistics (e.g., Bond et al., 2012; Carnell, 2008; Cladera et al., 2018, 2019; Comas et al., 2017; Hannigan et al., 2014; Mills, 2004; Nascimento et al., 2012; Stanisavljevic et al., 2014; Tempelaar et al., 2006). It is frequent to hear from lecturers and researchers that students have negative attitudes towards statistics. However, many studies that use scales to measure these attitudes observe that the mean values of the attitudinal dimensions are slightly above the value corresponding to indifference, if not for all, then for some dimensions. Frequently, the dimension related to the discipline difficulty obtains a lower evaluation. It seems that similar findings arise in the field of econometrics.

Table 2 also presents the differences in the attitudinal items and components for the students of the matched sample - those who answered pre-and post-test questionnaires. To analyse the changes in attitudes from the beginning to the end of the course, only the responses of the students who answered both questionnaires are used, following the practice followed in most previous investigations and that of the creator of the SATS (Schau & Emmioğlu, 2012).

When comparing the results of the pre and post-questionnaires, there are hardly any differences in the mean scores. Following the recommendations of the creator of the original SATS, differences from 0.5 are considered of practical significance (Millar & Schau, 2010; Schau & Emmioğlu, 2012). In this sense, as for the average scores of the six dimensions, only the Effort component shows a significant difference; Table 2 reports that the mean score of this dimension decreases significantly from the pre-test to the post-test questionnaire. The analysis of differences between the mean scores of attitudinal components in the pre and post-test was complemented by conducting paired sample tests: the t-test for normally distributed components and the Wilcoxon

test for non-normal components. Statistically significant differences were observed for the Value and Effort components. However, since the decrease in Value is less than 0.5, it is not considered to be of practical significance.

The results obtained agree with other investigations on attitudes towards Statistics. Some of these studies do not observe significant differences in attitudes at the end of the course (see, for instance, Evans, 2007; MacArthur & Santo, 2022). Others find that students' attitudes worsen during the course, being worse at the end than at the beginning (Apichatibutarapong, 2014; Bateiha et al., 2020; Bond et al., 2012; Carnell, 2008; Cladera et al., 2021; Herman & Kerby-Helm, 2022; Mutambayi et al., 2016; Schau, 2003a; Schau & Emmioğlu, 2012).

Table 2. Means and difference scores for items and subscales of the SATS, and the significance of the difference score tests for the subscales.

<i>Items and dimensions</i>	Total sample				Matched sample					
	<i>Pre-test Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Post-test Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Pre-test Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Post-test Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Difference score Mean SD</i>	
Affect	4.07	1.22	3.82	1.37	4.11	1.18	4.13	1.39	0.03	1.17
3 I have liked econometrics	4.67	1.54	4.43	1.67	4.70	1.46	4.64	1.66	-0.06	1.66
^R 4. I still feel insecure when I have to do econometrics exercises	3.63	1.58	3.23	1.72	3.80	1.59	3.26	1.76	-0.54	1.58
^R 15. I have felt frustrated going over econometrics tests in class	4.32	1.87	3.68	1.92	4.12	1.85	4.02	1.97	-0.10	2.06
^R 18. I have been under stress during econometrics classes	3.27	1.94	3.39	1.98	3.20	2.01	3.84	2.06	0.64	1.92
19 I have enjoyed taking econometrics courses	4.13	1.59	3.69	1.75	4.22	1.56	4.08	1.84	-0.14	1.95
^R 28. I am scared by Econometrics	4.41	2.05	4.49	2.04	4.60	1.84	4.96	1.87	0.36	1.61
Cognitive Competence	4.78	0.97	4.52	1.00	4.84	0.94	4.68	1.09	-0.16	0.93
^R 5. I have had trouble understanding econometrics because of how I think	4.24	1.64	3.76	1.66	4.28	1.58	4.08	1.70	-0.20	1.32
^R 11. I have no idea of what's going on in this Econometrics course	5.66	1.36	5.80	1.25	5.66	1.30	5.76	1.38	0.10	1.49
^R 26. I have made a lot of math errors in econometrics	4.43	1.70	4.86	1.48	4.60	1.70	4.88	1.55	0.28	1.80
31 I could learn econometrics	5.59	1.18	4.84	1.31	5.62	1.24	5.02	1.39	-0.60	1.69
32 I will understand econometrics equations	4.99	1.32	4.39	1.44	5.02	1.24	4.60	1.44	-0.42	1.60
^R 35. I have found it difficult to understand econometrics concepts	3.80	1.54	3.50	1.59	3.88	1.47	3.76	1.65	-0.12	1.73
Value	4.94	0.92	4.48	1.10	4.95	0.92	4.62	1.13	-0.33**	0.79
^R 7. Econometrics is worthless	6.28	1.08	5.89	1.35	6.38	0.97	6.12	1.21	-0.26	1.16
9 Econometrics should be a required part of my professional training	5.08	1.47	4.72	1.67	5.26	1.51	4.88	1.72	-0.38	1.66
10 Econometrics skills will make me more employable	4.90	1.47	4.50	1.57	4.76	1.61	4.64	1.57	-0.12	1.86
^R 13. Econometrics is not useful to the typical professional	5.17	1.44	4.76	1.55	5.08	1.34	4.82	1.45	-0.26	1.55
^R 16. Econometric thinking is not applicable in my life outside my job	4.89	1.47	4.34	1.75	4.98	1.29	4.50	1.71	-0.48	1.74
17 I use econometrics in my everyday life	3.23	1.39	2.91	1.39	3.08	1.19	3.08	1.50	0.00	1.25
^R 21. Econometric knowledge is rarely presented in everyday life	4.73	1.60	4.07	1.75	4.72	1.57	4.16	1.83	-0.56	1.86
^R 25. I will have no application for econometrics in my profession	4.96	1.76	4.61	1.80	5.02	1.71	4.70	1.78	-0.32	1.46
^R 33. Econometrics is irrelevant in my life	5.26	1.55	4.55	1.74	5.28	1.51	4.72	1.76	-0.56	1.51
Difficulty	3.26	0.78	3.28	0.85	3.36	0.78	3.42	0.80	0.06	0.82
6 Econometrics formulas are easy to understand	3.55	1.34	3.20	1.38	3.64	1.51	3.40	1.37	-0.24	1.65
^R 8. Econometrics is a complicated subject	3.19	1.60	2.95	1.51	3.26	1.60	3.28	1.53	0.02	1.72
22 Econometrics is a subject quickly learned by most people	2.55	1.23	2.28	1.26	2.48	1.09	2.48	1.34	0.00	1.39
^R 24. Learning econometrics requires a great deal of discipline	2.55	1.45	2.65	1.46	2.62	1.47	2.70	1.43	0.08	1.76
^R 30. Econometrics involves massive computations	3.84	1.73	4.69	1.62	4.04	1.69	4.68	1.62	0.64	1.76
^R 34. Econometrics is highly technical	3.29	1.35	3.23	1.42	3.34	1.41	3.42	1.37	0.08	1.71

R36. Most people have to learn a new way of thinking to do econometrics	3.81	1.38	3.99	1.51	4.12	1.44	3.98	1.52	-0.14	1.65		
Interest	4.99	1.32	4.40	1.56	4.93	1.46	4.70	1.63	-0.23	1.64		
12 I am interested in being able to communicate econometric information to others	4.86	1.57	4.23	1.83	4.74	1.61	4.54	1.86	-0.20	1.85		
20 I am interested in using econometrics	4.75	1.54	4.18	1.72	4.60	1.74	4.40	1.82	-0.20	1.84		
23 I am interested in understanding econometric information	5.23	1.48	4.70	1.66	5.26	1.56	5.04	1.60	-0.22	1.79		
29 I am interested in learning more econometrics	5.13	1.65	4.49	1.75	5.10	1.72	4.82	1.81	-0.28	1.93		
Effort	6.09	0.92	5.29	1.09	6.15	0.96	5.31	1.22	-0.84***	1.24		
1 I have done all my econometrics assignments	6.44	0.96	5.97	1.29	6.50	0.95	5.96	1.41	-0.54	1.42		
2 I have worked hard in my econometrics course	6.17	0.97	5.39	1.36	6.10	0.95	5.26	1.48	-0.84	1.53		
14 I have studied hard for every econometrics test	5.69	1.28	4.47	1.41	5.82	1.22	4.32	1.49	-1.50	1.46		
27 I have attended every econometrics class session	6.07	1.35	5.31	1.70	6.18	1.40	5.70	1.64	-0.48	1.93		
n				103				74				50

R: item reversed

Note: *** significant at 1%, ** significant at 5%.

Differences in attitudes towards econometrics by gender

Students' attitudes at the beginning and end of the course have been analysed by gender. It has also been investigated whether the difference scores between the pre-test and the post-test vary for men and women. Results are reported in Table 3, and Table 4 reports the value of the differences in the attitudes assessment between men and women for both the total and the matched sample.

When considering the pre and post-attitudes of men and women, as it happens with the joint sample, the attitudes in general are neutral or positive for all the components, except for Difficulty (Table 3). In the pre-test sample, the differences between women and men are neutral or positive in favour of women (Table 4). The highest difference is for the Value component (0.56 larger for women than for men), which is practically and statistically significant. However, considering the post-test sample, this positive difference has disappeared at the end of the course and has a slightly negative value. In the post-test sample, only the Effort dimension shows a positive difference greater than 0.5 in favour of women, which is also statistically significant. This difference is higher than in the pre-test sample, indicating that for women, the perception of the effort invested in the subject at the end of the course is significantly higher than that for men. For the rest of the components, the differences between women and men in the post-test are slightly negative, except for Cognitive Competence, which is lightly positive in favour of women but not significant.

As for the difference scores in the matched sample, both men and women exhibit a significant decrease in the Effort component, higher for men than for women (Table 3). Men did not present other significant differences in the rest of the components. However, women also show a significant decrease in their assessment of the Value component. The difference score for women is close to the critical value of -0.5 for the Interest component and exhibits a significance value only slightly above 10% (0.111). Therefore, for these two components, there is a higher reduction in their assessment for women than for men, for whom there are no significant changes.

In the matched sample, the pre-test assessment for the Interest dimension was 0.58 higher for women than for men (Table 4). This difference practically disappears at the end of the course (0.09). As for Effort, the assessment was higher for women than men at the beginning and end of the course. However, the difference increased at the end of the course, showing that the discrepancy between women and men in the perception of the required effort has increased throughout the course. As for the Value dimension, the difference in the mean scores of women and men moves from 0.36 in the pre-test to 0.03 in the post-test.

In general, the pattern observed is that women's attitudes have worsened to a greater extent than that of men (Table 4), since in the components in which there was a positive difference in favour of women, it disappears, and in some cases, it becomes negative at the end of the course; in those components in which the difference was already negative, it worsens further.

The analysis of Tables 3 and 4 shows that there are indeed significant differences in attitudes by gender. In general, attitudes are better among women at the beginning of the course, even in items of dimensions in which men generally have better attitudes, such as Cognitive Competence. However, the women's advantage disappears for almost all the components at the end of the course.

Table 3. Mean scores for attitude items and dimensions by gender and significance of the difference score tests.

<i>Items and dimensions</i>	Total sample				Matched sample					
	<i>Pre-test</i>		<i>Post-test</i>		<i>Pre-test</i>		<i>Post-test</i>		<i>Difference score</i>	
	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>
Affect	4.02	4.14	3.86	3.77	4.12	4.09	4.19	4.07	0.07	-0.03
3 I have liked econometrics	4.53	4.86	4.49	4.37	4.56	4.87	4.67	4.61	0.11	-0.26
^R 4. I still feel insecure when I have to do econometrics exercises	3.55	3.74	3.28	3.17	3.74	3.87	3.15	3.39	-0.59	-0.48
^R 15. I have felt frustrated going over econometrics tests in class	4.32	4.33	3.56	3.80	4.26	3.96	3.96	4.09	-0.30	0.13
^R 18. I have been under stress during econometrics classes	3.38	3.12	3.56	3.20	3.48	2.87	4.15	3.48	0.67	0.61
19 I have enjoyed taking econometrics courses	3.90	4.44	3.69	3.69	3.96	4.52	4.07	4.09	0.11	-0.43
^R 28. I am scared by econometrics	4.45	4.35	4.56	4.40	4.70	4.48	5.15	4.74	0.44	0.26
Cognitive Competence	4.69	4.92	4.37	4.70	4.70	5.01	4.50	4.90	-0.20	-0.12
^R 5. I have had trouble understanding econometrics because of how I think	4.15	4.37	3.77	3.74	4.04	4.57	3.96	4.22	-0.07	-0.35
^R 11. I have no idea of what's going on in this econometrics course	5.40	6.02	5.56	6.06	5.56	5.78	5.52	6.04	-0.04	0.26
^R 26. I have made a lot of math errors in econometrics	4.40	4.47	4.54	5.23	4.41	4.83	4.48	5.35	0.07	0.52
31 I could learn econometrics	5.52	5.70	4.64	5.06	5.56	5.70	4.70	5.39	-0.85	-0.30
32 I will understand econometrics equations	4.93	5.07	4.31	4.49	5.04	5.00	4.52	4.70	-0.52	-0.30
^R 35. I have found it difficult to understand econometrics concepts	3.72	3.91	3.41	3.60	3.59	4.22	3.81	3.70	0.22	-0.52
Value	4.71	5.27	4.58	4.38	4.79	5.14	4.61	4.64	-0.18	-0.50
^R 7. Econometrics is worthless	6.00	6.67	5.97	5.80	6.22	6.57	5.89	6.39	-0.33	-0.17
9 Econometrics should be a required part of my professional training	4.98	5.21	4.85	4.57	5.19	5.35	5.00	4.74	-0.19	-0.61
10 Econometrics skills will make me more employable	4.88	4.93	4.69	4.29	4.70	4.83	4.85	4.39	0.15	-0.43
^R 13. Econometrics is not useful to the typical professional	4.83	5.63	4.92	4.57	4.89	5.30	4.81	4.83	-0.07	-0.48
^R 16. Econometric thinking is not applicable in my life outside my job	4.65	5.23	4.31	4.37	4.85	5.13	4.33	4.70	-0.52	-0.43
17 I use econometrics in my everyday life	3.15	3.35	3.18	2.60	3.04	3.13	3.37	2.74	0.33	-0.39
^R 21. Econometric knowledge is rarely presented in everyday life	4.40	5.19	4.05	4.09	4.30	5.22	4.04	4.30	-0.26	-0.91
^R 25. I will have no application for econometrics in my profession	4.58	5.49	4.67	4.54	4.74	5.35	4.56	4.87	-0.19	-0.48

^R 33. Econometrics is irrelevant in my life	4.92	5.74	4.54	4.57	5.15	5.43	4.63	4.83	-0.52	-0.61
Difficulty	3.22	3.31	3.30	3.26	3.34	3.38	3.49	3.34	0.15	-0.04
6 Econometrics formulas are easy to understand	3.53	3.58	3.21	3.20	3.74	3.52	3.48	3.30	-0.26	-0.22
^R 8. Econometrics is a complicated subject	3.12	3.30	2.97	2.91	3.00	3.57	3.37	3.17	0.37	-0.39
22 Econometrics is a subject quickly learned by most people	2.85	2.14	2.41	2.14	2.74	2.17	2.67	2.26	-0.07	0.09
^R 24. Learning econometrics requires a great deal of discipline	2.68	2.37	2.85	2.43	2.93	2.26	3.00	2.35	0.07	0.09
^R 30. Econometrics involves massive computations	3.38	4.49	4.54	4.86	3.74	4.39	4.26	5.17	0.52	0.78
^R 34. Econometrics is highly technical	3.17	3.47	3.26	3.20	3.19	3.52	3.63	3.17	0.44	-0.35
^R 36. Most people have to learn a new way of thinking to do econometrics	3.78	3.84	3.90	4.09	4.04	4.22	4.00	3.96	-0.04	-0.26
Interest	4.84	5.21	4.49	4.29	4.66	5.24	4.66	4.75	0.00	-0.49
12 I am interested in being able to communicate econometric information to others	4.67	5.14	4.38	4.06	4.44	5.09	4.52	4.57	0.07	-0.52
20 I am interested in using econometrics	4.63	4.91	4.44	3.89	4.41	4.83	4.56	4.22	0.15	-0.61
23 I am interested in understanding econometric information	5.07	5.47	4.67	4.74	5.00	5.57	4.85	5.26	-0.15	-0.30
29 I am interested in learning more econometrics	4.98	5.33	4.49	4.49	4.78	5.48	4.70	4.96	-0.07	-0.52
Effort	6.02	6.19	4.97	5.64	5.96	6.37	4.87	5.83	-1.09***	-0.54**
1 I have done all my econometrics assignments	6.40	6.49	5.62	6.37	6.44	6.57	5.44	6.57	-1.00	0.00
2 I have worked hard in my econometrics course	6.02	6.37	5.03	5.80	5.81	6.43	4.74	5.87	-1.07	-0.57
14 I have studied hard for every econometrics test	5.57	5.86	4.31	4.66	5.56	6.13	4.11	4.57	-1.44	-1.57
27 I have attended every econometrics class session	6.10	6.02	4.92	5.74	6.04	6.35	5.19	6.30	-0.85	-0.04
n	60	43	39	35	27	23	27	23	27	23

R: item reversed

Note: *** significant at 1%, ** significant at 5%, * significant at 10%.

Table 4. Differences in male and female assessment of the attitudinal items and dimensions (Female score – Male score), along with their significance.

	Total sample		Matched sample	
	Pre-test	Post-test	Pre-test	Post-test
Affect	0.12	-0.09	-0.02	-0.13
3 I have liked econometrics	0.33	-0.12	0.31	-0.06
^R 4. I still feel insecure when I have to do econometrics exercises	0.19	-0.11	0.13	0.24
^R 15. I have felt frustrated going over econometrics tests in class	0.01	0.24	-0.30	0.12
^R 18. I have been under stress during econometrics classes	-0.27	-0.36	-0.61	-0.67
19 I have enjoyed taking econometrics courses	0.54	0.00	0.56	0.02
^R 28. I am scared by econometrics	-0.10	-0.16	-0.23	-0.41
Cognitive Competence	0.24	0.32	0.32	0.40
^R 5. I have had trouble understanding econometrics because of how I think	0.22	-0.03	0.53	0.25
^R 11. I have no idea of what's going on in this econometrics course	0.62	0.49	0.23	0.52
^R 26. I have made a lot of math errors in econometrics	0.07	0.69	0.42	0.87
31 I could learn econometrics	0.18	0.42	0.14	0.69
32 I will understand econometrics equations	0.14	0.18	-0.04	0.18
^R 35. I have found it difficult to understand econometrics concepts	0.19	0.19	0.62	-0.12
Value	0.56***	-0.20	0.36	0.03
^R 7. Econometrics is worthless	0.67	-0.17	0.34	0.50
9 Econometrics should be a required part of my professional training	0.23	-0.28	0.16	-0.26
10 Econometrics skills will make me more employable	0.05	-0.40	0.13	-0.46
^R 13. Econometrics is not useful to the typical professional	0.79	-0.35	0.42	0.01
^R 16. Econometric thinking is not applicable in my life outside my job	0.58	0.06	0.28	0.36
17 I use econometrics in my everyday life	0.20	-0.58	0.09	-0.63
^R 21. Econometric knowledge is rarely presented in everyday life	0.79	0.03	0.92	0.27
^R 25. I will have no application for econometrics in my profession	0.91	-0.12	0.61	0.31
^R 33. Econometrics is irrelevant in my life	0.83	0.03	0.29	0.20
Difficulty	0.10	-0.04	0.04	-0.15
6 Econometrics formulas are easy to understand	0.05	-0.01	-0.22	-0.18
^R 8. Econometrics is a complicated subject	0.19	-0.06	0.57	-0.20
22 Econometrics is a subject quickly learned by most people	-0.71	-0.27	-0.57	-0.41
^R 24. Learning econometrics requires a great deal of discipline	-0.31	-0.42	-0.67	-0.65

^R 30. Econometrics involves massive computations	1.11	0.32	0.65	0.91
^R 34. Econometrics is highly technical	0.30	-0.06	0.34	-0.46
^R 36. Most people have to learn a new way of thinking to do econometrics	0.05	0.19	0.18	-0.04
Interest	0.37	-0.20	0.58*	0.09
12 I am interested in being able to communicate econometric information to others	0.47	-0.32	0.65	0.05
20 I am interested in using econometrics	0.28	-0.55	0.42	-0.34
23 I am interested in understanding econometric information	0.40	0.07	0.57	0.41
29 I am interested in learning more econometrics	0.35	0.00	0.70	0.26
Effort	0.17*	0.68**	0.41**	0.96***
1 I have done all my econometrics assignments	0.09	0.75	0.13	1.13
2 I have worked hard in my econometrics course	0.35	0.77	0.62	1.13
14 I have studied hard for every econometrics test	0.29	0.35	0.57	0.46
27 I have attended every econometrics class session	-0.08	0.82	0.31	1.11

R: item reversed

Note: *** significant at 1%, ** significant at 5%, * significant at 10%.

Some previous studies obtain higher scores in some dimensions for women than for men (Cladera, 2021; Cladera et al., 2018, 2019; Opstad, 2020; Rejón-Guardia et al., 2019). As for attitudes towards Statistics, Cladera et al. (2018) observed a significant difference in Effort mean scores between men and women, with women having higher scores than men and no significant differences in the rest of the dimensions. Cladera et al. (2019) found that women have significantly higher mean scores than men in Affect and Self-confidence. Rejón-Guardia et al. (2019) observed that in four dimensions of the SATS-36, there were significant differences between men and women; in Affect, Value and Difficulty, the scores of women were lower than those of men, while in the Effort dimension, the attitudes of women were better than those of men. Opstad (2020) also reported gender differences in students' attitudes towards Statistics in all six SATS components, with males scoring higher than women in all components except Effort, in which women show a significantly higher average score than men. As for attitudes towards econometrics, Cladera (2021) found that women exhibit higher assessments for the Difficulty and Effort dimensions than men without having significant differences in the other components.

Differences in attitudes towards econometrics by other students' characteristics

The existence of differences in attitudes depending on academic and demographic characteristics other than gender was also studied.

Table 5 presents the mean scores of the attitudinal dimensions by students' characteristics for the pre and post-test. Difference scores between pre and post-test for the matched sample are also reported, as long as the significance of the tests for the equality of means.

Table 5. Mean values of the attitudinal components, difference scores, and significance of the tests for the equality of means by students' characteristics.

	Total sample												Matched sample									
	Pre-test						Post-test						Difference score									
	n	A	C	V	D	I	E	n	A	C	V	D	I	E	n	A	C	V	D	I	E	
Level of interest (significance)		**	**	***	*	***	***		***	**	***											
Very small / Small	17	3.3	4.3	4.8	2.9	4.4	5.6	6	3.6	3.9	4.4	3.1	4.8	5.1	6	0.3	-0.1	-0.4	0.1	0.5	-0.5	
Medium	57	4.1	4.8	4.7	3.4	4.6	6.0	30	4.0	4.5	4.3	3.4	4.3	5.2	30	0.1	-0.2	-0.4	0.0	-0.1	-0.9	
High / Very high	29	4.4	5.1	5.5	3.2	6.0	6.5	14	4.7	5.3	5.4	3.5	5.4	5.7	14	-0.2	-0.1	-0.2	0.2	-0.8	-0.9	
Grade in Statistics (significance)											*					*		**				
Failed	3	3.6	5.3	5.1	3.0	5.2	6.3	2	5.3	5.9	5.8	3.9	5.3	6.3	2	2.0	0.9	0.6	1.1	-0.3	-0.4	
Pass	57	4.0	4.8	4.8	3.4	4.8	6.0	24	4.1	4.4	4.3	3.4	4.3	5.2	24	0.0	-0.3	-0.5	-0.1	-0.4	-1.0	
Remarkable or Excellent	39	4.1	4.8	5.2	3.1	5.3	6.2	23	4.1	4.9	4.8	3.4	5.1	5.4	23	-0.2	-0.1	-0.3	0.2	-0.2	-0.7	
Maths usual grade (significance)		**											***								**	
Failed	5	3.6	4.3	5.2	3.1	5.1	5.9	1	5.7	4.3	5.2	2.6	6.5	5.8	1	1.7	0.7	0.0	0.6	1.8	-0.8	
Pass	17	3.9	4.3	4.6	3.2	4.9	6.0	5	4.5	4.3	4.7	3.7	3.8	3.4	5	-0.1	-0.3	0.0	0.3	-1.1	-2.4	
Remarkable or Excellent	81	4.1	4.9	5.0	3.3	5.0	6.1	44	4.1	4.7	4.6	3.4	4.8	5.5	44	0.0	-0.2	-0.4	0.0	-0.2	-0.7	
Expected grade (significance)		***	***	***	**	**			**	***	***		***		**	*			*	*		
Failed	1	2.3	2.7	4.8	2.3	3.3	6.0	1	3.0	2.8	4.9	2.3	4.8	5.0	1	0.7	0.2	0.1	0.0	1.5	-1.0	
Pass	63	3.7	4.5	4.7	3.1	4.8	6.2	33	3.8	4.3	4.2	3.4	4.0	5.0	33	-0.1	-0.4	-0.5	0.1	-0.6	-1.1	
Remarkable or Excellent	39	4.7	5.2	5.3	3.5	5.4	6.0	16	4.9	5.5	5.5	3.6	6.1	5.9	16	0.2	0.3	0.0	0.1	0.5	-0.3	
Usefulness (significance)		***	***	***		***	**		**	***	***		**								*	
Not at all / Not very useful	22	3.5	4.3	4.1	3.0	4.4	6.1	12	3.3	4.0	3.8	3.2	3.8	4.8	12	-0.4	-0.6	-0.4	-0.1	-0.4	-1.5	
Quite useful	49	4.0	4.7	4.9	3.4	4.6	5.8	22	4.1	4.6	4.5	3.4	4.6	5.4	22	0.2	-0.1	-0.5	-0.1	0.0	-0.5	
Useful / Very useful	32	4.6	5.3	5.6	3.2	6.0	6.4	16	4.8	5.3	5.4	3.6	5.6	5.6	16	0.2	0.1	-0.1	0.3	-0.5	-0.8	

Note: A (Affect), C (Cognitive Competence), V (Value), D (Difficulty), I (Interest), E (Effort). *** significant at 1%, ** significant at 5%, * significant at 10%.

Regarding the prior interest in the subject, there are differences of practical and statistical significance (0.5 or higher) in all the components at the beginning of the course. In the post-test, differences of practical significance are observed in all components except Difficulty, although only Affect, Cognitive Competence, and Value are statistically significant. As expected, the pattern is that students with higher scores are those more interested in the subject.

Relating the expected grade, results suggest that the higher the expected grade, the higher the attitudes mean scores. This finding agrees with research suggesting that attitudes influence expectancies (Hood et al., 2012). Additionally, students who believe that econometrics will be useful in their future careers tend to have more positive attitudes towards the subject, except for the Difficulty dimension, where there are no significant differences.

Discussion

According to the findings of this research, students' attitudes towards Econometrics are mostly neutral or positive at the beginning and end of the course. Only the assessment of the Difficulty dimension is slightly negative. These findings are consistent with previous research in the field of Statistics. Many lecturers perceive that students' attitudes towards the subject are negative, but when measured using scales, the results usually indicate that these attitudes are not so bad, at least for most of the components. Usually, the Difficulty dimension is the one with the lowest ratings. The results of this study, along with those obtained by Cladera (2021), seem to suggest that the same trend occurs for econometrics.

When investigating the differences in attitudes from the beginning to the end of the course, there is only a significant negative difference for the Effort component. This result also

agrees with those obtained in research on Statistics, in which attitudes are maintained or worsen throughout the course.

Regarding the differences by gender, at the beginning of the course, women's attitudes are similar to or better than those of men. However, at the end of the course, women only have significantly better mean scores than men for Effort and slightly higher, but not of practical significance, in Cognitive Competence.

As for the average difference scores between the post and the pre-test, there is a negative difference for both men and women in the Effort dimension. The decrease is higher for men than women. Men do not exhibit another significant pre-post-test difference score. However, the women's assessment of the Interest and Value dimensions decreases significantly throughout the course.

The findings confirm the hypotheses proposed in this research, as changes in attitudes have been observed from the beginning to the end of the course in some attitudinal dimensions, especially for women. Furthermore, as the second hypothesis stated, changes in attitudes differ between men and women.

The negative evolution of the Interest and Value attitudinal dimension for women is a worrying result, since for women, not only has the course not served to increase their interest in econometrics and improve their perception of the value of this subject, but at the end of the course these aspects have worsened. The data available in this research does not allow us to determine the reasons for this finding, so it is necessary to deepen the investigation of this issue in future studies. However, the literature on gender differences in economics studies provides arguments that could shed some light. Future works could explore them in the specific area of econometrics.

The greater initial interest of women in the subject of econometrics might be related to the fact that the lecturers of the surveyed students were also women. There is some evidence in the literature showing that having same-gender instructors improves the interest and performance of women (Carrell et al., 2010; Egalite & Kisida, 2018; Hwang & Fitzpatrick, 2021; Kricorian et al., 2020).

However, in the sample of this study, the highest interest of women in the subject disappears throughout the course. Though more research would be needed to unveil the reasons for this result, some explanations can be suggested. For instance, the decreasing interest of women after taking the course may be because they do not identify with Econometrics. Consequently, they are not attracted to the discipline. One reason could be that the applications of the courses focus on examples in which women are less interested, such as business applications rather than social welfare analysis (Bansak & Starr, 2010).

In turn, the decreasing interest might relate to the lack of representation of women in textbooks and class materials. Stevenson & Zlotnick (2018b) examine the frequency and ways of appearance of men and women in principles of economics textbooks. They reveal the

underrepresentation of women. The same was already observed decades ago by Feiner (1993), and does not seem to have changed much. Consequently, Stevenson & Zlotnick (2018) suggest that women might not feel identified and lose interest in economics courses. This reasoning might help explain the results obtained in this study about women's loss of interest in econometrics throughout the course. On the other hand, Wang & Degol (2013) mention the importance of sexist stereotypes in the different interests between men and women. In this sense, given that women tend to have a lower interest in STEM studies (since they are stereotypically male studies), realizing over the course that the subject of econometrics has a high mathematical and quantitative component could explain their loss of interest in it.

Another issue that could be related to the results obtained in this work could be the stereotype threat, "a widely studied psychological phenomenon that can occur in high-stakes settings and affects students who belong to groups that are the subject of negative stereotypes" (Bottan et al., 2022, p. 2). Many econometric studies focus on the disadvantaged position of women, such as wage gaps between men and women or lower likelihood of accessing managerial positions. Female students facing all these negative evidence and examples might feel the burden of the negative stereotypes, which would reflect in poorer attitudes.

In this line, Wang & Degol (2013) noted that some research implied that the combination of stereotype threat (believing girls are not good at math) and viewing math ability as a trait, not malleable, can lead to self-defeating beliefs about ability and decreased motivation and interest in pursuing math-related careers (Dweck, 2007). Consequently, in the field of STEM, some works have proposed the implementation of growth mindset interventions to strengthen beliefs in intelligence as malleable and discrediting gender-math stereotypes (Fabert, 2014; Law et al., 2021).

In summary, the results obtained in this work raise some gender-related concerns regarding students' attitudes towards Econometrics. Specifically, the main finding is that women start with better attitudes than men, although for some components, their attitudes decrease more throughout the course. So, in general, in the end, the positive gap in favour of women has almost disappeared or even is reversed, observing that the attitudes of women worsen in a higher proportion than those of men for four components.

Theoretical and practical implications

This work constitutes a novel contribution to the scarce literature on students' attitudes towards econometrics. On one hand, it analyses for the first time the evolution of attitudes throughout the course from a gender perspective. On the other hand, it illustrates how this analysis is framed within the context of Eccles' Expectancy-Value Theory, paving the way for future research advancements in this line. The door is open for analysing other factors that may affect students' attitudes since, according to the Expectancy-Value Theory, students' characteristics and previous achievement-related experiences influence attitudes.

From a practical standpoint, the findings support the importance of monitoring students' attitudes and their differences based on gender. Faced with the loss of interest and perception of the value of econometrics by women during the course, the implementation of measures aimed at avoiding it should be considered, such as innovative teaching methodologies, the use of inclusive materials with topics that equally interest both men and women or presenting female role models.

Given the results, it would be advisable to prevent women from losing interest during econometrics courses by making them identify with and feel more represented by the contents and materials of the subject. In this sense, in the field of economics, the American Economic Association (American Economic Association, 2023) makes some suggestions, such as the replacement of those examples that can be considered trivial or sexist (e.g., beer and sports cars) with diverse applications (e.g., inequality and climate change), or having same-gender lecturers since it has shown to improve the performance of students in underrepresented groups (Bansak & Starr, 2010; Carrell et al., 2010; Egalite & Kisida, 2018; Fairlie et al., 2014; Hwang & Fitzpatrick, 2021; Lusher et al., 2018). Stevenson & Zlotnick (2018) also propose to talk to students about textbook biases and complement them by exposing students to the diversity of research and researchers within economics. Jensen & Owen (2000) find that talking in class about topics traditionally considered of interest to women increases not only the confidence and courage of women but also of men. Porter & Serra (2020) show that role model interventions significantly impact female outcomes when studying economics and increase the number of women majoring in economics. Similarly, Avilova & Goldin (2020) conducted the *Undergraduate Women in Economics (UWE) Challenge* and concluded that role models, mentoring programs, providing students with resources to their liking, and supporting clubs and conferences increase women's interest in economics. Although not investigated in the field of economics, further research could also explore growth mindset interventions to promote in female students the mindset that intelligence is malleable and reduce belief in gender stereotypes regarding econometrics, as has been done in other areas such as STEM (Fabert, 2014; Law et al., 2021).

Educational institutions should facilitate and promote the implementation of the mentioned and other adequate measures to keep female students engaged and interested in the subject and prevent them from losing interest during econometrics courses. So, further research should address the study of the mechanisms that universities and other institutions can apply to encourage and support lecturers.

Limitations and further research

This work is the first to investigate the evolution of students' attitudes towards econometrics throughout the course and its relationship with gender. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct more studies to verify if similar findings are obtained in other contexts (e.g., different universities or countries). In addition, it is crucial to investigate the reasons behind the worrying

results regarding the decline in interest and the perception of the value of econometrics among female students throughout the course.

While the results highlight the divergent evolution of attitudes towards econometrics between men and women during the course, the collected data does not allow for understanding the reasons behind such differences. Therefore, further investigating this issue from a qualitative perspective would be advisable. For instance, conducting a qualitative study on a sample of female econometrics students would help identify the factors driving the loss of interest in the subject among women over the course.

Another point worth further investigation is that, despite extensive literature highlighting the lower preference of women for STEM disciplines, when measuring attitudes towards econometrics, it is observed that women have better attitudes than men in various components at the beginning of the course. Studies with larger samples from different universities and countries would allow for a deeper analysis to determine if this result is generalizable. Additionally, complementing the quantitative analysis with a qualitative examination of the reasons motivating the evaluations that males and females give to their attitudes would enrich the analysis. These analyses would deepen the understanding of why the observed differences occur.

The assessment of the effect of specific interventions on attitudes and their evolution, as well as gender differences, such as innovative teaching methodologies, growth mindset interventions, models of female economists and econometricians, and materials with inclusive examples, among others, is another research pathway.

Disclosure statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the authors, upon reasonable request.

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